

InVEST® MODEL – TOOL GUIDE MANUAL

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE MANUAL

This manual is a guide on how to estimate carbon storage values and carbon sequestration rates in an investigation site by using the [InVEST®](#) Carbon Storage and Sequestration model version 3.15.1.

The purpose of this guide is to give the reader an overview of what information is needed about the investigation site, what input data is required for the correct use of the model, and how to process the output data of the model. Furthermore, step-by-step instructions are given to perform the InVEST model and to process the output data from the model in MS Excel.

The focus of this guide are areas that lie in the temperate zone and which are mainly covered by wetlands, including river floodplains, alluvial forests, peatlands, bogs and marshes. This does not mean that the same method could not be applied to other ecosystems.

It is a prerequisite for the user to have basic knowledge in MS Excel and in a GIS mapping software, like QGIS or ArcGIS.

2 INVEST CARBON STORAGE AND SEQUESTRATION MODEL

The Natural Capital Project developed relatively simple models to quantify and map different ecosystem services. The quantification of carbon in a study area can be done by using the InVEST Carbon Storage and Sequestration model.

The InVEST model on carbon storage and sequestration is an extremely simple model to either estimate carbon storage and/or carbon sequestration rates in a landscape. For both estimations, the model needs information on four carbon pools (above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, values on soil carbon and on dead organic matter), the same as land cover / land use (LCLU) maps of the investigation area. The carbon pools need to be defined for each LCLU type in the investigated landscape. The LCLU maps can be of any time period for the carbon storage calculation. If carbon sequestration rates are to be calculated, LCLU maps of different time periods are needed.

2.1 LIMITATIONS OF THE MODEL

The InVEST Carbon Storage and Sequestration model oversimplifies the natural carbon cycle and assumes a linear change in carbon sequestration rates over time.

The model only relies on land cover or land use changes and does not account for carbon sequestration rates over time in an unchanged landscape. This means that if the land cover

is forested land, the carbon stock will remain identical for each year if the extent of the forested area remains the same throughout the chosen time periods. Furthermore, the carbon stock changes that will occur in the biomass of a growing tree will not be considered in the model, the same as the carbon that would be transformed from one carbon pool to another pool.

Additionally, climate factors like precipitation or temperature and other external factors like flood events are not considered in the model, but they could have a big impact on the changing carbon stock of a landscape.

The model can only be as accurate as the input data on the LCLU carbon pools, and the accuracy and resolution of the LCLU maps.

2.2 DOWNLOADING INVEST WORKBENCH

The InVEST Workbench gives access to all the available InVEST models. Note that only the model on Carbon is relevant for this guide. The InVEST Workbench can be downloaded from the following website:

<https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest/invest-downloads-data>

A detailed description on how to properly install the InVEST Workbench is given on the following website:

https://storage.googleapis.com/releases.naturalcapitalproject.org/invest-userguide/latest/en/getting_started.html#installing-invest-workbench-on-your-windows-computer

3 INVESTIGATION SITE

The investigation site is the area of which one wants to estimate the carbon storage or carbon sequestration.

In this chapter, the data sets which are needed about the investigation site is described. This information is important especially for defining the four carbon pools of each LCLU type within the site.

3.1 DATA REQUIREMENTS

The necessary information about the investigation site includes the climate region, soil types within the site, and LCLU maps.

3.1.1 CLIMATE REGION

The climate region of the investigation site can be defined by following the “classification scheme for default climate regions” published by the IPCC (IPCC, 2006) (Figure 1). Location specific criteria are needed to define the specific climate region within the temperate zone; they include mean annual temperature (MAT), the number of frost days, and the ratio between mean annual precipitation and potential evaporation (MAP:PET).

Another option to define the climate region is to consider the Köppen climate classification. These classifications are usually displayed as maps. However, one must be careful in choosing a map as they are subject to change due to climate changing factors. Thus, the publication year of the map is an important aspect to consider.

FIGURE 1. CLASSIFICATION SCHEME FOR DEFAULT CLIMATE REGIONS. THE CLASSIFICATION IS BASED ON MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE (MAT), MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION (MAP), MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION TO POTENTIAL EVAPOTRANSPIRATION RATIO (MAP:PET), AND FROST OCCURRENCE. (ADAPTED FROM IPCC, 2006)

3.1.2 SOIL TYPES

In order to estimate carbon stocks in the soils of the investigation site, the types of soil have to be identified. Usually, regional maps of the distribution of soils are available. In case there are no such information at one's disposal, there are however options on how to figure out the soil types of the investigation site.

The European Soil Bureau Network published the Soil Atlas of Europe which covers most of the European soil at a scale between 1:50.000 and 1:250.000. The soil classification system is based on the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB). The 2005 version of the atlas can be consulted at the website <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-atlas-europe>. A new version of the Soil Atlas was published in November 2024. One has to consider that the maps of the soil atlas can be less accurate than detailed maps of the region in question.

Another option is to perform soil surveys in the investigation site. However, it is more time and cost intensive.

3.1.3 LCLU MAPS

Land cover/land use (LCLU) maps exist in a variety of resolutions and detail. It is important to have a LCLU map in raster format which covers the full extent of the investigation area.

Copernicus provides LCLU maps free of charge, like CORINE Land Cover, and Riparian Zones Land Cover/Land Use. CORINE Land Cover is available as raster with a resolution of 100 meters and a thematic accuracy of at least 85%. The product is updated every six years and datasets are available for the years 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018. Riparian Zones Land Cover/Land Use map is only available as vector for 2012 and 2018. They have a minimum mapping unit of 0.5 ha and a minimum mapping width of 10m. For the Austrian country, another LCLU map is available, namely the EUNIS habitat map. It can be downloaded, free of charge, from the website [data.gv.at \(https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/1d1a8d2d-cfe8-46ef-aeda-136c88726b5d#resources\)](https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/1d1a8d2d-cfe8-46ef-aeda-136c88726b5d#resources). EUNIS habitat map is a raster with a resolution of 10 by 10 meters and is available for the year 2018.

All three LCLU maps are suitable for running the model. However, the Riparian Zones LCLU map is only available as vector and has to be rasterized first; in a GIS mapping software there are tools available to perform this transformation. It is suggested to use the most recent LCLU map for running the model. Furthermore, the highest the resolution, the more detailed the LCLU information and the thereof resulting carbon storage and carbon sequestration rates.

3.2 CARBON POOLS

For the InVEST model, information on four different carbon pools is needed: above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, soil, and dead organic matter. Above-ground biomass is defined as all the plant material that grows above the soil and is living, including tree trunks, bark, branches, and leaves. Below-ground biomass comprises all the living plant material that

grows in the soil and are part of the above-ground biomass, like the living root systems. Soil organic matter encompasses the soil organic components. Dead organic matter comprises the non-living plant matter above the soil including litter, woody debris, and standing and downed dead trees.

All four carbon pools need to be defined for each LCLU class of the investigation area. The unit for the carbon pools need to be metric tons of carbon per hectare (tC/ha).

3.2.1 LCLU CLASSES

The information on the LCLU classes within the investigation area can be extracted from the LCLU maps. The main LCLU types can be forests, grasslands, croplands, inland wetlands, urban areas, and water bodies. Depending on the accuracy and resolution of the LCLU maps, more LCLU classes can be entailed within that main LCLU type. This means that for the main LCLU type forest, the LCLU classes of deciduous forest and/or coniferous forests could be present.

3.2.2 CARBON POOL ESTIMATIONS

In order to define the carbon pools, a list with all the occurring LCLU classes is needed. Once the classes are known, information on the carbon stock for each of the four carbon pools can be gathered.

Estimating carbon stocks for each carbon pool can be challenging. Therefore, this author created the Excel workbook “Carbon_pools_guide” that can be used as a means of estimating the different carbon pools for a variety of LCLU classes based on a literature review. If needed, the user has the option to add own values to the list. The focus of the manual lies mainly on wetland and floodplain ecosystems in the temperate region.

4 CARBON STORAGE AND SEQUESTRATION

Carbon storage and carbon sequestration can be estimated by applying the InVEST Carbon Storage and Carbon Sequestration model. Once the necessary information is gathered, the data needs to be prepared in a specific manner to properly run the model. Afterwards, the outputs need to be processed and carbon stocks and/or carbon sequestration rates can be calculated. Figure 2 represents a workflow of the work steps, including the data pre- and post-processing in a GIS mapping software.

For the purpose of this manual, the example of the implementation site “March-Thaya Floodplains” is given in order to show how the InVEST model could be applied in estimating carbon storage and/or carbon sequestration in a temperate wetland. At the end of this chapter, a variety of scenarios are shown; they include temporal changes in carbon sequestration values, and a sensitivity analysis of carbon stocks based on varying carbon pool values, and different LCLU maps.

FIGURE 2. WORKFLOW OF THE DATA PROCESSING IN A GIS MAPPING SOFTWARE, THE INVEST MODEL, AND MS EXCEL.

4.1 INVEST MODEL GUIDE

This chapter provides instructions on how to prepare the model inputs, as well as step-by-step instructions on how to run the model. Additionally, the model outputs are described in further detail.

4.1.1 INPUT DATA

For the InVEST Carbon Storage and Carbon Sequestration model, two sets of input information are needed: raster layer(s) of the investigation area, and the carbon pool values for the LCLU classes prepared as CSV file.

4.1.1.1 LCLU RASTER MAP

The LCLU maps need to be in raster format (.tif). If only vector maps are available, they have to be transformed into a raster. For the InVEST model, the LCLU map needs to be delimited by the investigation area and it is this raster that is used as input. From this delimited raster, the LCLU classes can be extracted through histograms and the LCLU classes are described as unique values.

In case the model is used to estimate carbon storage, one map of a chosen time period is sufficient. For carbon sequestration estimates, two LCLU maps of different time periods are necessary. It is important to note that both raster files need to be perfectly aligned, the resolution identical.

Example:

For the March–Thaya floodplain, the EUNIS habitat map was used for modeling carbon storage and CORINE LC maps of the years 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018 were used for modelling past carbon sequestration. LCLU classes were extracted from both the EUNIS habitat map and CORINE LC maps.

Code	LCLU_name_L1	LCLU_name_L4	LCLU_area_ha
1279	Water	Surface standing waters	37.12
1363	Water	Surface running waters	8.03
1392	Water	Permanent non-tidal, smooth-flowing watercourses	15.85
1863	Grassland	Grasslands and lands dominated by forbs, mosses or lichens	0.11
1864	Grassland	Dry grasslands	86.58
2182	Grassland	Mesic grasslands	14.8
2193	Grassland	Low and medium altitude hay meadows	53.51
2230	Grassland	Agriculturally-improved, re-seeded and heavily fertilised grassland, including sports fields and grass lawns	0.19
3449	Forest	Broadleaved deciduous woodland	645.6
4339	Forest	Coniferous woodland	12.57
4824	Forest	Mixed deciduous and coniferous woodland	15.22
4850	Forest	Lines of trees, small anthropogenic woodlands, recently felled woodland, early-stage woodland and coppice	4.68
5158	Cropland	Arable land and market gardens	8.02
5159	Cropland	Intensive unmixing crops	3.92
5168	Cropland	Bare tilled, fallow or recently abandoned arable land	30.37

FIGURE 3. LEFT: DELIMITED RASTER OF THE IMPLEMENTATION SITE (IS1). RIGHT: LCLU CLASSES OF THE SITE WITH ITS CODE, GROUPS OF LCLU TYPE, SPECIFIC LCLU CLASSES AND AREA.

Figure 3 illustrates the example of the March–Thaya floodplain with the EUNIS habitat map and its corresponding LCLU classes.

4.1.1.2 CARBON POOLS CSV

Once the LCLU classes are known, the four carbon pools need to be defined for each LCLU class and the information prepared in a tabular structure.

For the model, a CSV file is needed as input data. The CSV file should describe each LCLU class present in the investigation site with its LCLU code, its LCLU name, and its four carbon pools. Each LCLU code needs to be unique. As for the carbon pools, the unit must be in metric tons per hectare (t/ha). Furthermore, the No-Data value of the raster needs to be included in the list with the value of zero for all four carbon pools.

The following table shows how the CSV file should be structured in order to be able to upload the file into the InVEST model:

lucode	LCLU_name	C_above	C_below	C_soil	C_dead
integer	text	number [t/ha]	number [t/ha]	number [t/ha]	number [t/ha]

It is important to note that all LCLU classes need to be represented in the table as it leads to errors in the model, if otherwise.

Example:

In the implementation site “March–Thaya Floodplains”, 15 LCLU classes were identified (see Figure 3). In the table below (Table 1), the four carbon pools are represented for each LCLU class, the same as the No-Data value. These carbon pool values were gained through literature research.

TABLE 1. CARBON POOL VALUES FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION SITE (IS1).

lucode	LCLU_name	C_above	C_below	C_soil	C_dead
1279	Surface standing waters	0	0	0	0
1363	Surface running waters	0	0	0	0
1392	Permanent non-tidal, smooth-flowing watercourses	0	0	0	0
1863	Grasslands and lands dominated by forbs, mosses or lichens	1	2	212	0
1864	Dry grasslands	2	3	97	0
2182	Mesic grasslands	3	1	338	0
2193	Low and medium altitude hay meadows	3	1	212	0
2230	Agriculturally-improved, re-seeded and heavily fertilised grassland, including sports fields and grass lawns	2	7	212	0
3449	Broadleaved deciduous woodland	281	80	186	9
4339	Coniferous woodland	163	20	154	22
4824	Mixed deciduous and coniferous woodland	222	50	170	10
4850	Lines of trees, small anthropogenic woodlands, recently felled woodland, early-stage woodland and coppice	35	20	176	5
5158	Arable land and market gardens	0	0	88	5
5159	Intensive unmixed crops	0	0	88	5
5168	Bare tilled, fallow or recently abandoned arable land	0	0	88	0
-1	NoData	0	0	0	0

4.1.2 STEP-BY-STEP MODEL USE

First, open the InVEST Workbench. A list with all the available models appears and out of this list select the “Carbon Storage and Sequestration” model. A new tab opens in which the user can start uploading the necessary files for running the model (Figure 4).

“Workspace” is the folder into which the outputs of the model will be saved. “File Suffix” is optional and the chosen suffix will be added to the name of the output file. “Baseline LCLU” is the LCLU map of the investigation area in raster format. “Carbon Pools” is the CSV file with the codes of all the LCLU classes and their carbon pool values. “Calculate Sequestration” needs to be checked if the model is used to calculate carbon sequestration. “Alternate LCLU” is the LCLU map of the investigation area of a later time period than the “Baseline LCLU”.

Carbon Storage and Sequestration x

Workspace (directory)	<input type="text" value="directory"/>	<input type="button" value="x"/>	<input type="button" value="folder"/>
File Suffix (text, optional)	<input type="text" value="text"/>		
Baseline LULC (raster)	<input type="text" value="raster"/>	<input type="button" value="x"/>	<input type="button" value="folder"/>
Carbon Pools (csv)	<input type="text" value="csv"/>	<input type="button" value="x"/>	<input type="button" value="folder"/>
Calculate Sequestration	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Alternate LULC (raster)	<input type="text" value="raster"/>		<input type="button" value="folder"/>

FIGURE 4. INTERFACE OF THE INVEST CARBON STORAGE AND SEQUESTRATION MODEL.

In order to run the model for carbon storage, chose a workspace on your computer, select the LCLU map of the investigation site (.tif) and the corresponding carbon pools (.csv). The suffix is optional but helps to distinguish the model outputs if the model is applied more than once. Once all four entries are chosen, press "Run".

Example for calculating carbon storage:

Carbon Storage and Sequestration x

Workspace (directory)	<input type="text" value="S1_InVEST_data\IS1_InVEST_data_output\L4"/>	<input type="button" value="check"/>	<input type="button" value="folder"/>
File Suffix (text, optional)	<input type="text" value="_L4"/>	<input type="button" value="check"/>	
Baseline LULC (raster)	<input type="text" value="IS1_InVEST_data_input\eunis_IS1_mask.tif"/>	<input type="button" value="check"/>	<input type="button" value="folder"/>
Carbon Pools (csv)	<input type="text" value="nVEST_data_input\carbon_pools_IS1_L4.csv"/>	<input type="button" value="check"/>	<input type="button" value="folder"/>

In case the model is used to calculate carbon sequestration, additionally click on the toggle switch button and select the second LCLU map. This second LCLU map needs to be of a later time period than the first. Remember that the LCLU classes of both LCLU maps need to be listed in the carbon pools file and that they need to have the same resolution and cover the same area.

Example for calculating carbon sequestration:

✓ Carbon Storage and Sequestration ×
⚙

Workspace (directory)	<input type="text" value="..\InVEST_data_output\Sequestration\CORINE ✓"/>	📁
File Suffix (text, optional)	<input type="text" value="CLC_90-00 ✓"/>	✓
Baseline LULC (raster)	<input type="text" value="..ta\IS1_InVEST_data_input\IS1_CLC1990.tif ✓"/>	📁
Carbon Pools (csv)	<input type="text" value="..lata_input\carbon_pools_IS1_L4_CORINE.csv ✓"/>	📁
Calculate Sequestration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Alternate LULC (raster)	<input type="text" value="..ta\IS1_InVEST_data_input\IS1_CLC2000.tif ✓"/>	📁

4.1.3 OUTPUT DATA

The outputs of the model consist of a folder with the intermediate outputs, namely raster files with the above-ground, below-ground, dead, and soil carbon values, then a task graph cache folder, a text file of the parameter log, a HTML file of the report, and a raster file with the sum of all values of the four carbon pools. If the model was used to calculate carbon sequestration, the folder with the intermediate outputs contains the raster files of the current/baseline and the future/alternate carbon values; the raster files containing the baseline carbon values are labelled with “bas” (for “baseline”), whereas the raster files containing the alternate carbon values are labelled with “alt” (for “alternate”). Additionally, the output also contains a raster file with the changes between the baseline and alternate carbon storage values. The carbon values of all raster files have a unit of metric tons per hectare.

Example:

Figure 5 shows the outputs of the model after running the calculations for carbon storage in the implementation site March-Thaya floodplains.

FIGURE 5. MODEL OUTPUTS AFTER CARBON STORAGE CALCULATIONS.

4.2 DATA PROCESSING IN GIS

The raster files from the model's output can be opened in a GIS mapping software. In order to extract the information of the raster files, histograms can be created. The area which is used to delimitate the raster should be the same than which was used for delimitating the LCLU maps. Furthermore, if histograms are created, one has to make sure that no prefix is defined for the outcome, as this will interfere with the subsequent calculations! Once the histograms are created, copy the information from the attribute table into MS Excel.

Example:

*After running the InVEST model on carbon storage in the implementation site of the March-Thaya floodplains, all five outcome raster files were imported into QGIS. The data included the raster files with the information on the carbon values of the above-ground (*c_above_bas_L4*), below-ground (*c_below_bas_L4*), dead (*c_dead_bas_L4*), soil (*c_soil_bas_L4*), and total (*c_storage_bas_L4*) carbon stocks. A representation of a raster layer is shown in Figure 6.*

FIGURE 6. REPRESENTATION OF THE RASTER WITH THE ABOVE-GROUND CARBON VALUES.

Then histograms were created for each raster using the tool “Zonal Histogram” (see Figure 7). Note that no prefix was defined for the output column. The layers of the histograms for above-ground, below-ground, dead, and soil carbon values were further merged into one layer. In the attribute table, the carbon values of all four features are grouped.

FIGURE 7. REPRESENTATION OF THE WORKSTEPS IN QGIS.

The layers of the histograms do not need to be merged into one layer; however, it might be easier to continue with the carbon stock calculations.

4.3 CARBON STOCK CALCULATIONS

After extracting the carbon values from the raster files, and copying the information from the attribute table into MS Excel, the data can be used to calculate the carbon stock of the investigation area.

It is important to note the different units which are associated with the cells of the table. The header has the unit of metric tons per hectare and the cells in the table’s body are the count of pixels (Figure 8). The number of pixels needs to be converted into hectare; the pixel size can be looked up in the raster layer properties. Since the data from the table’s header contains valuable information, it is crucial not to define a prefix for the header in previous data processing steps.

FIGURE 8. UNITS OF THE CELLS IN THE ATTRIBUTE TABLE.

The goal is to multiply the areal density by the converted number of pixels and calculate the sum of the products for each carbon pool. For this the SUMPRODUCT function in MS Excel can be used.

Example:

The information on the attribute table was copied into MS Excel:

Import attribute table from "histo_c_bas_L4_merge"																											
fid	area_ha	0	1	2	3	35	163	222	281	7	20	50	80	5	9	10	22	88	97	154	170	176	186	212	338	layer	
1	936.57	10331	11	8677	6831	488	1257	1522	64560	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	histo_c_above_bas_L4
2	936.57	10331	6831	11	8658	0	0	0	0	19	1725	1522	64560	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	histo_c_below_bas_L4
3	936.57	24656	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1662	64560	1522	1257	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	histo_c_dead_bas_L4
4	936.57	6100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4231	8658	1257	1522	468	64560	5381	1480	histo_c_soil_bas_L4

The carbon pools were written in front of the carbon values and the number of the pixels were converted into hectare (original pixel size: 100m² = 0.01 ha):

Add carbon pool source and convert pixel to hectare																											
Header: tC/ha; table values: ha (converted from pixel size of 0.01ha)																											
Carbon pool	0	1	2	3	35	163	222	281	7	20	50	80	5	9	10	22	88	97	154	170	176	186	212	338			
above	103.31	0.11	86.77	68.31	4.68	12.57	15.22	645.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
below	103.31	68.31	0.11	86.58	0	0	0	0	0.19	17.25	15.22	645.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
dead	246.56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.62	645.6	15.22	12.57	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
soil	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	42.31	86.58	12.57	15.22	4.68	645.6	53.81	14.8		

The function SUMPRODUCT was applied for each carbon pool to calculate the carbon stock of each carbon pool. Then the sum of all carbon stocks was calculated:

Add carbon pool source and convert pixel to hectare																											
Header: tC/ha; table values: ha (converted from pixel size of 0.01ha)																											
Carbon pool	0	1	2	3	35	163	222	281	7	20	50	80	5	9	10	22	88	97	154	170	176	186	212	338			
above	103.31	0.11	86.77	68.31	4.68	12.57	15.22	645.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
below	103.31	68.31	0.11	86.58	0	0	0	0	0.19	17.25	15.22	645.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
dead	246.56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.62	645.6	15.22	12.57	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
soil	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	42.31	86.58	12.57	15.22	4.68	645.6	53.81	14.8		
Calculate total carbon stock per pool																											
Carbon pool	Carbon stock [tC]																										
above	187 383.73	=SUMPRODUCT(\$B\$12:\$Y\$12;B13:Y13)																									
below	53 083.60																										
dead	6 322.24																										
soil	153 960.12																										
total	400 749.69																										

In the implementation site "March-Thaya Floodplains", the carbon stock for the above-ground carbon pool was estimated at 187,384 tC, the below-ground carbon pool at 53,084 tC, the dead organic matter carbon pool at 6,322 tC, the soil carbon pool at 153,960 tC, and the total carbon stock at 400,750 tC (Table 2).

TABLE 2. CARBON STOCK VALUES.

Carbon pools	Carbon stock [tC]
Above	187,384
Below	53,084
Dead	6,322
Soil	153,960
Total	400,750

The carbon stocks were estimated on two levels of detail based on the EUNIS habitat LCLU classes. L1 has the lowest level of detail, whereas L4 has the highest level of detail to describe the LCLU classes. The juxtaposition of the carbon stock calculations of both levels of detail are represented in Figure 9. There is no discrepancy seen between the carbon stock values of the pools; the total carbon stock is around 3% higher for the lower level of detail (L1), which is not considered significant in this carbon stock estimation.

FIGURE 9. CARBON STOCK ESTIMATES BASED ON EUNIS HABITAT LCLU CLASSES.

4.4 CARBON SEQUESTRATION CALCULATIONS

Carbon sequestration is calculated the same way than the carbon stocks described in the previous chapter. Additionally, the carbon stocks of two or more time periods need to be calculated. Since the InVEST model only computes outputs based on two time steps, one needs to run the model several times if more time steps are required.

Once the carbon stock values (C) are calculated for each time period (t), the change between the current (baseline) and future (alternate) values can be defined, the same as the yearly carbon sequestration rate. The latter is calculated by dividing the difference of the carbon values of both time steps by the years between these time steps:

$$\Delta C = \frac{C_{alt} - C_{bas}}{t_{alt} - t_{bas}}$$

It is important to note again that the InVEST model is a simple model and does not account for the complexity of the natural carbon cycle. Thus, carbon sequestration rates can be zero in case the LCLU classes have not changed in the two investigated time periods.

Example:

In the implementation site “March–Thaya Floodplains”, carbon sequestration changes were calculated based on CORINE LC maps from the years 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018. Figure 10 represents the carbon stock values for each of these time steps. It can be seen that the carbon values of each carbon pool are similar for each year; however, the above-ground carbon pool for the year 2000, and the thereof resulting total carbon stock, is lower compared to the other years.

FIGURE 10. CARBON STOCK VALUES FOR THE YEARS 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, AND 2018.

In the time period between 1990 and 2000, the above-ground carbon pool decreased by 20%, the below-ground carbon pool by 15%, the dead organic matter carbon pool by 6%, and the soil carbon pool increased by 4%; in total, the carbon stock decreased by 9%. From the year 2000 to 2006, the above-ground carbon pool increased again by 15%, the below-ground carbon pool by 11%, the dead organic matter and soil carbon pools by 3%; the total carbon stock increased again by 9%. The above-ground, below-ground and dead organic matter carbon pools further increased by 1% between 2006 and 2012. There was no carbon stock change in the total carbon stock during this time period. Furthermore, the carbon stock remained unchanged between the years 2012 and 2018 (Figure 11).

FIGURE 11. CARBON STOCK CHANGES FOR THE TIME INTERVALS OF 1990–2000, 2000–2006, 2006–2012, AND 2012–2018.

The yearly carbon sequestration rates and the yearly share of carbon change are represented in (Figure 12). Considering the yearly changes in carbon stock within the four time intervals, the above-ground carbon pool decreased yearly by 2% (3566 tC/yr) from 1990 to 2000, then increased yearly by 2.4% (5160 tC/yr) from 2000 to 2006, and it increased yearly by 0.1% (278 tC/yr) between 2006 and 2000. There was no carbon sequestration recorded between 2012 and 2018. The carbon sequestered in the below-ground carbon pool dropped 1.5% per year (822 tC/yr) during 1990 and 2000, then it grew 1.9% per year (1155 tC/yr) between 2000 and 2006 and 0.1% per year (78 tC/yr) between 2006 and 2000. There was no carbon sequestered in the below-ground carbon pool between 2012 and 2018. The dead organic carbon pool showed a yearly decrease of 0.6% (40 tC/yr) between 1990 until 2000, then the yearly carbon stock increased 0.5% (35 tC/yr) from 2000 to 2006, and 0.1% (9 tC/yr) from 2006–2012. It did not change between 2012 and 2018. A 0.4% (795 tC/yr) of soil carbon was sequestered yearly between 1990 and 2000, 0.6% (1074 tC/yr) between 2000 and 2006. There was a yearly decrease of 0.1% (152 tC/yr) from 2006 and 2012, and no change in soil carbon sequestration was detected during the years 2012 until 2018. The total yearly carbon sequestration rate of the implementation site was negative 0.9% (3633 tC/yr) from 1990 until 2000. During the years 2000 until 2006, the yearly carbon sequestration rate was 1.6% (7424 tC/yr), and between 2006 and 2018, there was no significant yearly change of the total carbon sequestration registered.

Overall, according to the CORINE LC maps, the carbon stock and carbon sequestration rates have not much changed in the implementation site from 1990 until 2018. Between 1990 and 2018, the carbon stock increased 339 tC/yr which is less than 0.001% per year.

FIGURE 12. LEFT: YEARLY CARBON SEQUESTRATION RATES FOR THE TIME INTERVALS 1990–2000, 2000–2006, 2006–2012, AND 2012–2018. RIGHT: SHARE OF YEARLY CARBON SEQUESTRATION FOR THE TIME INTERVALS 1990–2000, 2000–2006, 2006–2012, AND 2012–2018.

For the carbon sequestration calculations of the implementation site, it should be noted that the CORINE LC maps have a low resolution of 100 meters. Thus, minor changes in the LCLU might not have been detected and the consequent modelling could not capture changes in carbon sequestration rates. However, the InVEST model can give some insights on the current (baseline) and past (alternate) carbon stock changes in the implementation site.

4.5 SCENARIOS

The InVEST model can be used to run a variety of scenarios. In this case different sensitivity analysis can be performed, it can either be based on varying carbon pool values and/or various types of LCLU maps.

In the following sub-chapters only examples for the implementation site “March–Thaya Floodplains” are given.

Example:

For the implementation site “March–Thaya Floodplains”, two sensitivity analyses were performed: one for different carbon pool values and one for different LCLU maps. Additionally, a scenario was run to estimate the future carbon stock of the implementation site.

4.5.1 CARBON POOL SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Example:

In the first sensitivity analysis, the carbon pool values were modified for three different scenarios, all based on the EUNIS habitat map (Figure 13). The first scenario was based on intuitive values from literature which reflected the main LCLU types of the implementation site. For most LCLU types only one value (best fit) was selected according to this author’s

expertise. The second scenario was based on more moderate values which represented calculated averages of all EUNIS habitat LCLU types that could potentially represent the investigation site; minimum and maximum values were included in the calculations. The third scenario was based on averages of the absolute minimum values that were found in literature and that could fit the EUNIS habitat LCLU types of the implementation site. These scenarios were performed for two levels of details of the LCLU classifications; L1 represents the less detailed classification and L3 or L4 the more detailed classification.

FIGURE 13. CARBON STOCKS FROM THE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS BASED ON CARBON POOL VALUES.

The results of the carbon pool sensitivity analysis show that the first (“intuitive”) scenario has the highest carbon stock values for the above-ground (190,700 tC for L1 and 187,200 tC for L4), below-ground (54,600 tC for L1 and 53,100 tC for L4), and soil carbon pools (162,700 tC for L1 and 154,000 tC for L4), the same as for the total carbon stock (414,300 tC for L1 and 400,500 tC for L4) of the implementation site. The carbon stocks of the dead organic matter lie between the scenarios “moderate” and “minimum” with the respective carbon stock values of 6,300 tC for both L1 and L4. There are minor differences in carbon stocks between the two levels of detail, L1 and L4. The total carbon stock was 13,800 tC higher when the lower level of detail of the LCLU classifications was applied.

For the second (“moderate”) scenario, the above-ground (117,300 tC for L1 and 115,500 tC for L4), soil (126,000 for L1 and 126,500 for L2) and total (282,800 tC for L1 and 305,100 tC for L4) carbon stock values lie between the values for the scenarios “intuitive” and “minimum”.

There is a larger discrepancy between the levels of detail for the below-ground, dead organic matter, and total carbon stocks; the below-ground carbon stock values were 34,200 tC for L1 and 53,200 tC for L2, and for the dead organic carbon stock they were 5,400 tC for L1 and 10,000 tC for L4. The total carbon stock was 22,270 tC higher for the more detailed level of the LCLU classifications.

The third (“minimum”) scenario showed that most carbon stocks were lower compared to the scenarios “intuitive” and “moderate”, exceptions were the below-ground (50,500 for L4) and dead organic matter (6,700 for L4) carbon stocks for the more detailed level of LCLU classes. For the below-ground and dead organic matter carbon stocks, the values of the lower level of detail were 27,700 tC and 2,100 tC, respectively. The carbon stock values were similar for the above-ground (86,600 tC for L1 and 91,200 for L4) and the soil (75,100 tC for L1 and 77,200 tC for L4) carbon pools. The total carbon stocks were 191,500 tC for L1 and 225,600 tC for L4; thus, the total carbon stock is 34,100 tC higher for the more detailed level of the LCLU classifications.

Overall, it can be said that the carbon stock in the implementation site is more dependent on the carbon stock values, than on the level of detail of the LCLU classifications. Furthermore, these scenarios are only an assumption, and especially the scenario “minimum” was merely created to define baseline carbon stock values. It might be highly unlikely that the carbon stock of the implementation site is as low as the outputs from the scenario “minimum”.

4.5.2 LAND COVER / LAND USE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Example:

In the second sensitivity analysis, three types of LCLU maps were used, namely the EUNIS habitat map, the Riparian Zones LCLU map, and the CORINE LC map (Figure 14). All three maps were from the reference year of 2018 and the scenarios were performed on the lower level of detail (L1) and the highest level of detail (L3 or L4). The carbon pool values for the scenarios were first defined for the EUNIS habitat LCLU classes and then applied to the other two LCLU maps.

The results show that the carbon stock for the CORINE LC was highest compared to the EUNIS habitat and Riparian Zones map with the values 214,200 tC for L1 and 214,300 tC for L3. The lowest values were 171,800 tC (L1) and 160,700 tC (L4) for the Riparian Zones map. The carbon stock values based on the EUNIS habitat map were 190,700 tC (L1) and 187,200 tC (L4) for the above-ground carbon pool stock. For the below-ground carbon stock values were lowest for the Riparian Zones map (49,400 tC for L1 and 46,700 tC for L4), followed by the values for the EUNIS habitat map (54,600 tC for L1 and 53,100 tC for L4) and highest for the CORINE LC map (61,100 tC for L1 and 61,300 tC for L3). A similar trend was observed for the carbon stock values for the dead organic carbon pool; the lowest values were simulated for the Riparian Zones map with 5,500 tC (L1) and 5,400 tC (L4), 6,300 tC (L1 and L4) for the EUNIS habitat map, and highest for the CORINE LC map with 7,400 tC for L1 and 6,900 tC for L3. The soil carbon stocks fluctuate more among the level of detail of the LCLU maps. For the

EUNIS habitat map, L1 had a higher carbon stock (162,700 tC) than L4 (154,000 tC). For the other two LCLU scenarios, the lower level of detail was lower compared to the higher level of detail; the Riparian Zones map had 173,900 tC for L1 and 201,600 tC for L4, and the CORINE LC map had 167,300 tC for L1 and 189,200 tC for L3. The total carbon stocks for the EUNIS scenario were 414,300 tC for L1 and 400,400 tC for L4. A little higher were the total carbon stocks based on the Riparian Zones map with 400,600 tC for L1 and 414,400 tC for L4. The highest total carbon stocks were calculated for the CORINE scenario with 450,000 tC (L1) and 471,700 tC (L3).

FIGURE 14. CARBON STOCKS FROM THE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS BASED ON LCLU MAPS.

The sensitivity analysis based on the different LCLU maps shows that the estimation of the total carbon stock is highest for the LCLU map with the lowest resolution, namely the CORINE LC map. The EUNIS habitat map and the Riparian LCLU map have the same resolution and their total carbon stock values are similar. However, this correlation does not imply causation.

4.5.3 PROGNOSIS FOR CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Example:

A prognosis was made of how much carbon could be sequestered in the implementation site "March-Thaya Floodplains" after 10 years since the publication of the EUNIS habitat map in 2018. Since the InVEST model cannot calculate carbon sequestration rates, the carbon pool values of a future scenario must be defined first. It was assumed that the carbon pool values

of the LCLU types grassland, cropland, and water remain identical over time. The reason for this assumption is a lack of literature on the carbon sequestration rates in these LCLU types. It was further assumed that the LCLU types in the implementation site would not change within this 10-year period. Hence, merely the future carbon pool values for the LCLU type forest were estimated. The carbon sequestration rates for the four carbon pools in forests were gathered from literature.

According to the IPCC (2006b), the approximate value for above-ground biomass growth in natural forests and forest plantations is 4.0 tonnes dry mass per hectare per year. For the simplicity of this scenario, the carbon fraction is estimated 0.5 tonne carbon per tonne dry mass. Thus, the above-ground carbon pool gains 2 tC/ha/year. A study by Coomes et al. (2012) modelled the net carbon sequestration rate of mountain beech trees (25 years old) based on long term data. The model revealed that the net sequestration in above-ground biomass was 2 tC/ha/year, which corresponds to the estimates published by IPCC (2006b).

There was no literature found on below-ground carbon sequestration rates in temperate wetland forests. Therefore, the ratio between the above-ground and below-ground carbon pool was calculated for the year 2018, and this ratio was used to estimate the carbon stock of the below-ground carbon pool after a 10-year period. Bernal & Mitsch (2012) described the carbon accumulation in soil of different riverine wetlands. For this analysis, the average carbon sequestration of their cases was calculated and resulted in 1.29 tC/ha/year. For the dead organic matter carbon pool, sequestration values were extracted from a study by Coomes et al. (2012). They stated that 1.15 tC/ha/year was related to leaf litter fall, 0.5 tC/ha/year to shedding of branches/twigs, and 0.64 tC/ha/year and 0.05 tC/ha/year was lost through the decomposition of coarse woody debris, and litter and humus, respectively. Meaning that 0.96 tC/ha/year was added to the dead organic matter carbon pool.

As input of the InVEST model the EUNIS habitat map was used for both, the baseline and the alternate (future) model. First, the carbon storage was modelled for the year 2018 based on the current estimates of the carbon pools. The carbon pool values were defined for the low level of detail (L1) of the LCLU map. Then, the same LCLU map was used with the adapted carbon pool values that could reflect the future.

Based on the estimated carbon sequestration rates, the total carbon stock in the implementation site could increase by 8% after 10 years (Figure 15), as the total carbon stock was estimated at 414,300 tC in 2018, and 447,500 tC 10 years later. The above-ground carbon stock was 190,700 tC in 2018, and estimated to be 204,400 tC in the future scenario. Thus, the above-ground carbon stock could increase by 7% after 10 years. The below-ground carbon pool could sequester 8% during that time period, as the carbon stock increased from 54,600 tC to 58,800 tC. The estimates for the dead organic carbon pool would have the greatest carbon sequestration rate; the model revealed that the dead organic carbon stock could increase from 6,300 tC to 12,800 tC, which is an increase of 103%. The soil carbon pool could increase by 5% during a 10-year time period; the soil carbon stock was 162,700 tC in 2018, and 171,500 tC in the future.

FIGURE 15. CARBON STOCK CHANGES AFTER A 10-YEAR PERIOD.

4.6 MODEL VALIDATION

Once the model was run, the model outputs ought to be validated by comparing the results to either remote sensing data or in-situ data, such as forestry data and sampling data. The higher the data quality, the better the model outputs can be assessed for its accuracy.

Example:

For the implementation site “March-Thaya Floodplains”, the InVEST model outputs of the above-ground forest carbon pool were compared to satellite and in-situ data (Figure 16).

The model outputs only describe the above-ground carbon stock available in the forested areas of the implementation site. The other LCLU classes were neglected in this comparison due to a lack of available data to compare all carbon pools. Furthermore, the before-mentioned scenarios “minimum”, “moderate”, and “intuitive” were included in the comparison.

Two satellite data sets were utilized, the first was “Forest biomass map of EU27 for 2020” (AGB 2020), which is a 100m resolution map of the forest aboveground woody biomass stock

in tons per hectare of the EU27 (Avitabile, 2022). It is based on the ESA CCI biomass map for 2018 and harmonized with the National Forest Inventory (NFI) to match the data at a sub-national level for the year 2020 (Avitabile et al., 2023). The second satellite data set was “ESA Biomass Climate Change Initiative” (AGB ESACCI), which is a 100m resolution map of the global above-ground biomass in tons per hectare of the year 2021.

Considering the in-situ data, two data sets were used, forestry data from the forest manager of the investigation site, and field data gathered from sampling. The forestry data included tree species distribution values and the stock of timber in cubic metres of the entire investigation site; it should be noted that the recorded stock of timber can be 10% to 15% higher in nature compared to the official records. The field data was collected from four randomly selected sites within the investigation site; 5 to 10 trees (in total 35 trees) were measured at each site in order to deduce above-ground carbon stock values, which were then extrapolated to the entire investigation site.

FIGURE 16. COMPARISON OF ABOVE-GROUND CARBON STOCKS.

Figure 16 shows that the above-ground carbon stock of the forested area varies between 32,150 tC and 41,560 tC for the satellite data and fluctuates between 42,430 tC and 49,730 tC for the in-situ data. The model outputs estimated 91,050 tC, 115,330 tC and 187,010 tC for the InVEST model scenarios “minimum”, “moderate” and “intuitive”, respectively. It can be seen that both, the satellite data and the in-situ data, estimated similar values for the above-ground carbon stock, whereas the InVEST model computed values twice to nearly four times higher. Since the model was based on data from literature, especially data from (unmanaged) floodplain ecosystems, and since the implementation site is mainly covered by managed forests, the input data are likely to not reflect the actual carbon stock of the implementation site.

5 LIMITATIONS

The InVEST model is a very simple model and can calculate the carbon stock of an area based on LCLU maps and carbon pool values, the latter are dependent on the expert's judgement.

For the example on the carbon stock estimates of the implementation site "March-Thaya Floodplains" the carbon pool values were solely obtained through literature research, making the model output quite dependent on the accuracy of the literature values and on the transferability of the data to other ecosystems. As seen in the sensitivity analysis the carbon stocks can vary greatly depending on the input of the carbon pool values.

Furthermore, the results of the carbon sequestration model only provide carbon sequestration rates if the land cover type is changing during the assessed time periods. Thus, the model does not consider that more carbon may be stored in a system if vegetation, especially trees, grows. A simple solution to this limitation would be to classify forested land as "young" in the first time period and as "old" in the following time period. Then, the carbon pool values for the growing forest can be calculated manually and the carbon pool values can be adapted for the later time period. In literature, reference values are available to calculate carbon sequestration in certain types of vegetation. This would give the user the opportunity to consider growth in biomass and thus increasing carbon stock values for the investigation area. Nevertheless, these assumptions are linked to further uncertainties and raises the question of transferability.

The model validation revealed that both satellite and in-situ data implied lower above-ground carbon stocks for the implementation site than the InVEST model estimations. This discrepancy in carbon stocks could have several reasons. As mentioned before, the input values were based on literature, especially carbon pool values obtained through field measurements in extensively managed floodplain systems or nature protection zones. Managed forest systems tend to have a reduced above-ground biomass due to the management practices, such as homogenous age distribution, limited species composition (Erb, 2004), reduced presence of understory and herbaceous biomass, removal of dead wood, and tree maintenance. According to Erb (2004), forest management practices accounted for a 30% reduction in above-ground carbon stocks in Austrian forests, compared to forest ecosystems in the absence of anthropogenic activities. Moreover, the satellite data on above-ground biomass was calibrated with values of national forest inventories, which might enhance the issue of an inaccurate account of above-ground carbon stocks in extensively managed ecosystems. Through the calibration of the satellite datasets, the pristine or extensively managed forest ecosystems are likely to be underrepresented which leads to an underestimation of carbon stocks in these systems.

Since the carbon stocks of the investigated site varied depending on the method, there was a strong need to verify the outcomes. Hence, a published field study investigating carbon stocks in a wetland was chosen and compared to carbon stock estimates from satellite data. A study by Cierjacks et al. (2010) assessed the above-ground carbon stock of riparian vegetation in the Donau-Auen National Park in Austria. The study area was around 1310 ha, within which 76 sampling sites were selected, representing all relevant vegetation types. By

only taking into account the above-ground carbon of the forested areas, the carbon stock was 218,220 tC for the entire study area. The sampling design is considered thorough and well-defined. Therefore, their study area was regarded as a suitable example for assessing the above-ground carbon stock via satellite data. For this purpose, the satellite data set “Forest biomass map of EU27 for 2020” (AGB 2020) was utilized. The total biomass of the beforementioned study area was calculated and converted to metric tons carbon per hectare. It was revealed that the thereof estimated carbon stock of the entire study area was 91,980 tC, indicating that the satellite data captured not even half of the carbon stock which was calculated by Cierjacks et al. (2010) (Figure 17).

FIGURE 17. ABOVE-GROUND CARBON STOCKS FROM SATELLITE DATA AND SAMPLING DATA.

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